

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Experimental Study of the Stability of a Low-Cost C-Band Active Reflector Using Sentinel-1 Imagery

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ABSTRACT The application of Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) interferometry (InSAR) techniques when in the imaged areas the coherence is low and persistent scatterers are missing often demands the installation of artificial reflectors, usually represented by passive corner reflectors (PCR). For missions based on C band sensors such as Sentinel-1, passive corner reflectors capable of providing a high phase accuracy are cumbersome and heavy, and their installation in hard places can be difficult and costly. The installation of active reflectors, compact and smaller with respect to passive corner reflectors, can sometimes represent a valid alternative but the use of these devices has not yet largely spread due to their high sensitivity to the seasonal temperature variation which can reduce their reliability both in amplitude and phase stability. This paper focuses on the analysis of the performance of a low-cost active reflector designed to operate with C band spaceborne radars, tested in a real field campaign using Sentinel-1 imagery. The goal is to assess through an experimental based approach the stability of this device, using data acquired during the monitoring campaign of a landslide based on InSAR. The stability of the Active Reflector (AR) installed in a stable area is analyzed to evaluate its performance when used as a reference in interferometric processing. The results of this study show a stability over a temporal lapse of almost three years equivalent in deformation measurement to a few millimeters accuracy, which can be considered a satisfactory goal for this InSAR application.

INDEX TERMS Calibration, deformation, interferometry, persistent scatterer (PS), synthetic aperture radar (SAR), transponder.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of Sentinel-1 SAR images for Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) applications in non-urban areas is often challenging, especially when they are covered by vegetation, snow, or with scenarios as temperate (warm) ice glaciers, which can be so geometrically and dielectrically instable to dramatically reduce the coherence. A too long revisit pass of the satellite mission can compromise the application of interferometric techniques. Within this context, a significant aid can be obtained by the presence of artificial targets in the site, easily detectable in the radar images and with a stable phase. These objects, which consist in bright

reflectors designed to perform a stable amplitude and phase response, can behave as Persistent Scatterer [1], improving image interpretation and providing reference pixels for radiometric and phasimetric calibration. In non-coherent regions, artificial reflectors as passive corner reflectors (PCR) are often installed and several papers deal with their test and application [2], [3], [4]; they usually consist in targets with a simple geometrical shape and designed to perform high radar reflectivity; the outstanding role in SAR observations of these targets is proved by several detailed studies issued in the last years [5], [6], [7], [8]. Usually, a PCR is a simple metal structure whose faces are oriented to maximize the energy reflected along the backscattering direction of the radar, and a size large with respect to the wavelength of the operating radar signal, to maximize the reflected energy. This kind of

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artificial reflectors are widely diffused and can often represent a reliable reference for interferometric data analysis also in interferometric measurements with geodetic purposes: an exhaustive description of the main characteristics of the most common PCR, the metal trihedral, is available in [9]. The main parameter determining the PCR phase stability, is its Radar Cross Section (RCS) measured in dBsm (dB relative to square meters) which is strictly related through the Radar equation to the intensity of the signal backscattered by the target to the radar receiving antenna. To evaluate the accuracy of a PCR in phase retrieval, its RCS must be compared to the signal background generated by the radar noise due to the distributed scatterer (DS) present in the surrounding area. To quantify this accuracy, the usual parameter to know is the Signal to Clutter Ratio (SCR), estimated through the ratio between the RCS of the target and the signal noise, namely the radar clutter, present in its surroundings. SCR is hence a metric for the received radar signal measurement quality and considering a typical scenario, the higher the RCS the better the accuracy achievable in interferometric phase retrieval [10]. The radar clutter is determined by the backscattering characteristics of the scenario, and it can be estimated from the satellite imagery: details about the SCR are given in the following section. When designed to be used for C band, the operating frequency of Sentinel-1 (S1), and even more with spaceborne radar operating at lower frequencies, the PCRs are bulky because the maximum achievable RCS is related to its size. This fact often results in further issues when hard weather conditions, such as heavy rainfall, strong winds and snowfall are frequently occurring in the installation site. In addition, their placement can be difficult in sites of hard accessibility as mountain slopes, glaciers etc. To improve their handling also the use of combined stacks of smaller PCRs has been recently proposed [11], but their installation is however not viable in difficult areas, as mountain slopes and glaciers where a low coherence or low Persistent Scatterers (PS) density is often expected. An alternative to the installation of these targets is the use of active reflectors (AR). For clarity to the reader, we specify that in this paper we use the term active reflector referring to moderate- to low-cost and easy to install devices in support to wide areas monitoring using SAR data. Transponders which are used for example for spaceborne system calibration during commissioning phases, although conceptually similar, are different [12], [13]. These systems are designed with more ambitious and different objectives and with high complexity and costs.

An AR in place of maximizing the RCS of the target through the size and the geometry of its design, employs an active Radio Frequency (RF) circuit to amplify the incoming signal and redirecting it toward the satellite, thus providing an equivalent high RCS but reducing the bulk and the weight of the target. As remarked in some studies, see for example [14], a transponder for spaceborne radar calibration in general suffers from a high sensitivity to temperature variations. For the same reason, the stability of the phase response of an

AR for field use can deteriorate over temporal intervals of months and years. The sensitivity of the AR response to thermal conditions is usually ascribed to the effect of the temperature on the RF section, where its active components can introduce instable amplitude and phase responses. This issue is linked to the own characteristics and performance of the components of the RF and on the design architecture of the device, and for this reason variable for different apparatus. It is common for example to detect a drift in the phase and amplitude response of the retransmitted signal. In high level transponder, thermostatic control system can be used to maintain the temperature of the system stable. A similar approach cannot be applied for the AR subject of this paper because it requires the availability of a complex electronic module which needs a considerable power source, which prevents this solution for field use. In fact, compact devices to be used in field are designed with the requirement of a low power consumption (typically a battery buffered by a solar panel) to make possible their installation in non-urban areas and challenging environments such as glaciers, mountain slopes, where they are usually employed. In the last decade, a commercial system namely the Electronic Corner Reflector (ECR-C) by Metasensing, has been made available to the market [15] and more recently a similar device has been proposed in [16]. To the author's knowledge, also confirmed in the recent paper discussing the potential and drawbacks of compact active transponders [17], only these two devices have been tested in the field: the ECR-C, whose performance has been discussed in various papers as for example in [18] and [19], and that used in this study. Research papers about the development of other innovative approaches such as "software-defined" prototype [20] have been also proposed but without any on field operative test in a real case. The C-band AR here tested proposes as an alternative to passive reflectors, especially when used for deformation monitoring; it has as main requirement the goal to provide a stable phase response with reduced encumbrance and energy consumption.

Generally speaking, as far as the importance to study the feasibility and reliability of ARs as an alternative to PCR, it is worth to note that a growing interest on developing ARs as alternative to PCRs can find an increasing interest for the incoming low frequency band (S, L and P band) satellite radar missions (e.g. NISAR and BIOMASS) because the size and weight of passive reflectors necessary to provide high RCS at these frequencies is clearly nearly impracticable [21].

This paper focuses on the assessment of the performance of a prototype developed and tested at CTTC for its use in an experimental campaign carried out in a vegetated area to assist the processing of S1 images, within a European project, namely EC project MOMPA (EFA295/19 FEDER - Interreg V-A) POCTEFA 2014-2020, aimed at landslide monitoring in a mountain area in Andorra. In this study, ground truths to validate the mechanical stability of the sensor for the entire AR acquisition duration analyzed were not

available. For this reason, the authors evaluate the performance of the AR only by applying a statistical analysis based on satellite data, assuming from experimental observations of previous investigations [22] that the location of the device is mechanically stable. The amplitude and interferometric phase temporal series here reported have been obtained processing a set of S1 SAR images, acquired for almost three years: from December 4, 2020, to August 3, 2023, corresponding to 114 S1 SLC images, in IW mode acquisition and descending orbit. The detectability and the phase stability of the device is here analyzed to estimate the final reliability and the achievable accuracy of the AR response when used for deformation monitoring.

The paper is structured as follows. After this introduction (I), a second section recalls the working principle of the AR including a brief description of the design rationale (II). A description of the experimental setup (III) and an analysis and a discussion of the results follow (IV); a conclusion section (V) completes the paper.

II. THE WORKING PRINCIPLE AND THE DEVICE

An AR basically consists of two antennas, one to receive the satellite signal and the second to retransmit it toward the satellite. The two antennas are connected through a RF circuit designed to amplify the intensity of the radar signal and powered by the energy available from an external electric source, as shown in fig. 1, where two simple schemes show the functioning principle of the AR and of a PCR are depicted. The passive reflector simply reflects the radar signal by means of its oriented metal plates; the AR amplifies and retransmits the received signal after amplifying it using the energy from an external power source.

FIGURE 1. Working principle of a PCR and of an AR. The first simply reflects the incoming signal while the AR amplifies and retransmits the received signal after amplifying it using the energy from an external power source.

The AR used in this study is a compact device whose design aimed at achieving a very low power consumption,

a low-cost, using of the shelf (OTS) components, and finally targeting to an accuracy adequate for landslides and slopes deformation monitoring. This goal is obtained using a simple radiofrequency architecture and achieving fair phase stability through a linear design [16]. To reduce the warmup effect, i.e. the effect of a thermal transient on the electronics and provide a stable inertial condition of the RF section, this device is based on a “always switched on” condition, a different choice with respect to the approach used in other ARs which activate the system only for a short lapse over the satellite overpass using an internal clock managed by a microprocessor [15]. The tested device includes two high gain patch array antennas specifically designed to minimize the gain requested from the amplifying section [23], thus minimizing the power consumption and at the same time avoiding excessive leakage between the two antennas which could compromise the AR proper functioning. Before installing the device in the test site, several preliminary tests have been carried out in laboratory and in controlled field campaigns: for an exhaustive technical description of the system refer to [16]; in table 1 the main characteristics of the system are reported.

TABLE 1. Active reflector characteristics.

Orbiting mode	Ascending or descending
Polarization	Single: Co- or Cross-pol
RCS	≥40 dBsm
Antenna gain	17 dB
RF gain	42 dB
Requested Power	< 0.1 A @ 12V
Operating band	5 405± 50 MHz
Dimensions	52 cm x 32 cm x 70 cm
Weight	< 10 Kg

The goal of an AR is to guarantee the presence in the acquired SAR image of a target with high and stable RCS; the contribution of this target must be much higher than that from other scatterers included in the same pixel associated to the target, ensuring that the measured signal is dominated by the amplitude and phase response of the AR. Furthermore, to minimize the error in phase measurement, the RCS of the target must be sufficiently higher than the reflections from the surrounding area (radar clutter) where it is installed: the signal backscattered to the spaceborne radar from the AR pixel must outstand among the signals generated by the surrounding pixels. The parameter associated with this performance is the SCR, which determines the minimum value of the RCS necessary to guarantee the expected phase accuracy. The effective phase error, ϵ , in radians, is usually estimated, for a stochastic backscattering environment, through the following formula [10]:

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2SCR}} \tag{1}$$

SCR can be calculated according to two different rationales based on the spatial or temporal ergodicity of the clutter respectively as recently discussed in [24]; in this study we

estimate the SCR averaging amplitude data from the temporal series of the S1 imagery. The RCS of the basic AR scheme can be calculated by using the simple formula (1), see for example [25], where G_{RF} is the gain of the RF amplifying section, G_{tx} and G_{rx} the transmitting and receiving antenna gain respectively, and λ the wavelength (5.5467 cm) corresponding to the center frequency of the Sentinel-1 signal bandwidth, 5.405 GHz.

$$RCS = GRF \frac{G_{tx}G_{rx}}{4\pi} \lambda^2 \quad (2)$$

The RF circuit includes active and passive microwave components which add a phase delay to the signal available from the receiving antenna terminals before to send it back to the AR transmitting antenna. In AR design it is important that this delay, added as a phase term to the radar signal redirected towards the satellite, does not significantly affect the focusing algorithm, avoiding that the AR signature is placed in pixels different from that corresponding to its actual location. This delay is generated by the RF components and their connections (cable and connectors); hence it can be estimated only by measuring it in the laboratory: the obtained value for our device corresponds to a spatial delay negligible with respect to the pixel size.

The gain of the two identical single patch array antennas specifically designed for this system, is 17 dB. The goal is to achieve an RCS of the AR ≥ 40 dBsm, a value elaborated from comments and calculations discussed in [16] and values available from [10] (see Table 1, pag. 6), to theoretically achieve a 0.1 mm accuracy in S1 IW mode imagery. To realize the improvement obtained using this AR (size: 52 cm x 32 cm x 70 cm) with respect to an equivalent PCR in terms of encumbrance it is worth noting that this value corresponds to the RCS of a triangular trihedral reflector whose size is 1.7m. Based on the previous consideration, finally the only parameter to settle is G_{RF} . A main issue is that G_{RF} cannot be arbitrarily high because it cannot exceed the coupling factor between the two antennas, to avoid an auto feed of the circuit which can saturate the AR and compromise its operation. The patch array antennas, size 14 cm x 14 cm x 0.5 cm, are separated by 30 cm, a trade-off between reducing the encumbrance of the device and minimizing the coupling due to the proximity between the two antennas. We estimated it through simulation and measurements carried out in an anechoic chamber. The value corresponding to the selected geometry is satisfactory: < -50 dB, thus, a $G_{RF} = 42$ dB was finally set. One of the design requirements was to maintain the current absorption of the RF section very low, to allow the use of a low power system, and at the same time to maintain the device always switched on for guaranteeing a stable response of the RF electronics. The AR was designed for S1 SAR, operating at C band (5.405 GHz \pm 50 MHz); it is necessary to choose one polarization configuration among the four possible co- and cross combinations (VV, HH, VH and HV). The AR can work also for RADARSAT and other

C band sensors whose bandwidth is not drastically different from that of S1.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. AR INSTALLATION

The field test of the AR has been carried out during the experimental activities organized within the project previously cited in the introduction. The main task of this project was monitoring an area threatened by a landslide, a rockslide probably induced by roadside excavations. In a previous study [22], the AR was used as reference point for the calculation of the interferometric phase of a set of PCRs, all distributed in a wide unstable area for monitoring purposes to provide a set of PS for the monitoring of a wide area. The orientation of the AR boresight is azimuth 100° (Nord) and elevation and 51° (East), its position: Long. 1.483412041666667, Lat. 42.448077296666666, altitude: 980. asl. The device was installed on a vegetated slope, and it is powered by a battery (12 V and 70 Ah capacity) and a solar panel (60 W). Fig. 2 shows a picture from Google Earth of the area with indicated the location of the AR, and a picture of the installation.

FIGURE 2. Picture of the area where the AR was installed. The red star indicates the location of the device: Long.: 1.483412041666667, Lat. 42.448077296666666, altitude: 980 m. The smaller picture shows the installation which includes the AR, the battery and the solar panel.

B. SENTINEL-1 IMAGE PROCESSING

The SAR imagery used in this work consists of 114 Sentinel-1 SLC images, descending pass (relative orbit number: 110), polarization: VV, acquired from December 4, 2020, to August 3, 2023. A total amount of 413 interferograms with maximum temporal baseline of 30 days were processed using CTTC Persistent Scatterer Interferometry (PSI) processing chain [26]. The Digital Elevation Model (DEM) available from the Shuttle Topographic Mission (SRTM) with 30 m resolution was used. For the interferometric processing IW mode acquisitions have been processed.

The outstanding contribution of the AR with respect to the background can be appreciated by observing fig. 3 obtained by calculating a mean amplitude image, through a coherent averaging with and without the AR. Fig. 3A map is calculated using 70 images when the AR was not present, while Fig. 3B is obtained with 114 images with the AR working. Both images show some further bright spots due to the PCRs installed in the area used in the cited monitoring campaign. The analysis of the response of these PCRs is reported in a previous paper [22] and it is out of scope of this paper; here we comment on data of backscattering amplitude from one PCR for improving the analysis of the AR behavior. In fig. 3B it is worth noting how the AR backscattered amplitude outstands with respect to those of square trihedral corner reflectors of limited size for installation constrains (the inner edge length is 0.60 m cm) which provide a maximum RCS= 32 dBsm at boresight. The phase data of these targets is not used in the next section dedicated to the phase analysis because they were installed in an unstable area.

FIGURE 3. Example of a mean amplitude image obtained averaging SLC data, (A) when the AR (sky circle) was not present, (B), AR switched on (red circle). Bright pixels in the two images are due to PCRs installed in the area: the yellow square indicates the one considered in the amplitude data analysis in this paper.

To analyze the amplitude response of the AR we use calibrated S1 Ground Range Detected (GRD) data. This is obtained calculating the radar brightness via S1 Look Up Table (LUT) coefficients, considering the pixel area and the incidence angle which maintained within 38.2° and 38.3° , as in [27]. This approach offers a resolution of 10 m by 10 m. We analyze the backscattering coefficient, σ_0 , of four targets: the AR a PCR, and two areas without any outstanding reflector or PS, taken as clutter representative; 166 images of VV polarization are analyzed; figure 4 shows the map of the mean value of the backscattering coefficient, σ_0 , acquired during January 2020 to June 2023 temporal interval.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION

A. TARGETS' CHARACTERIZATION

To evaluate the performance of the AR we analyzed the amplitude and the interferometric phase temporal series of the AR and of two clutter areas. The estimate of the SCR demands selecting targets and areas representative of the radar response in the imaged area. The statistical distribution

FIGURE 4. Map of the backscattering signal of the area selected for the SCR study: mean amplitude of GRD data. Legend unit decibels. Yellow star and red contours indicate the AR, and the areas used for estimating radar clutter respectively.

of the amplitude of the AR, when it behaves as a PS, is characterized by a Probability density function (Pdf) different from that of distributed homogeneous scatters representing the clutter, as exhaustively analyzed in [22] and [28]. Hence, as the first step we check the statistical reliability of the selected targets. Figs. 5 show the histograms of each temporal data set of the following four targets: a) the AR b) the PCR marked in fig.3 (which although installed in an unstable area maintained a stable backscattering amplitude), and c) and d), a spatial average calculated from pixels of the area selected in two different locations with different intensities, namely Ref clutter #1 and Ref clutter# 2. Figures 5a, 5b, 5c and 5d also show the fit curves of two different Pdf calculated using Rayleigh (violet line), and Rice (yellow line) functions respectively. The histograms shape of the radar response of the different targets confirm that AR and the PCR data set are well fitted by a Rice distribution associable to PSs. On the other hand, as expected, the distributed scatter clutter areas fit better a Rayleigh distribution, that confirms a behavior observed in previous studies [22], or [28] where the authors make a more detailed analysis and suggest different functions even.

B. AMPLITUDE

The study the amplitude stability of the AR relies on the value of the backscattering coefficient vs the acquisition date of the S1 images plotted as Fig. 6; three different targets are shown: the AR, and the average of 3×4 pixels for clutter area 1 and 2×2 for clutter area 2; for the sake of generality the two different clutter areas, namely Ref1 and Ref2 in fig. 4, have been selected with different average intensities. In AR response curve some data are missing due to battery drawbacks; of note that in one case (after 16 January 2022) the fall was progressive, and the device followed the slow decrease of the powering voltage. In the previous case the prompt interruption was ascribed to a cable issue and fixed promptly. The average and standard deviation of the three data sets are

FIGURE 5. Histograms of the backscattering coefficient, σ_0 , of the analyzed targets: AR (A), PCR (B), Clutter area #1 (C) and Clutter area #2 (D); the curves represent a Pdf fitting based on Rayleigh (violet line), and Rice (orange line) distribution respectively.

resumed in Table 2. The table reports the SCR calculated considering the clutter of the AR location estimated when it was not working, and with respect to the two different clutter areas.

FIGURE 6. Temporal series of the backscattering coefficient amplitude for three different targets: AR (blue points), four pixels average in clutter1 area (empty orange squares) and four pixels average in clutter2 area (green squares).

TABLE 2. Mean and standard deviation (STD) and SCR of the backscattering coefficient series for the three targets shown in fig.5.

Target	Mean (dB)	STD (dB)	SCR (dB)
AR	+11.23	0.838	+24.00 ¹⁾
Clutter area # 1	-11.93	1.276	+23.16 ²⁾
Clutter area # 2	-21.17	1.803	+32.40 ²⁾

1) Calculated with respect to AR switch off condition.
2) Calculated with respect to Clutter.

C. PHASE

The stability of the interferometric phase is analyzed in fig. 7 which shows the data retrieved from the interferometric processing for all the S1 images vs the acquisition date. It is evident from the graph the presence of a periodic behavior which can be correlated to the seasonal variation of the air temperature at the satellite pass time; Table 3 reports the mean, and the standard deviation of the displacement values plotted in fig.6. The AR is provided with a sensor which measures the temperature internal to the case. This allows estimating the degree of correlation and the sensitivity of the amplitude and phase of the received signal to the seasonal range of variation; we plotted the phase data vs the measured air temperature values in fig. 8. The correlation is very low (the correlation coefficient of the linear regression is $R^2 = 0.293$) and significantly lower than that obtained for a similar sensor in a previous test in a controlled environment [16]. It is confirmed that a general increase of the phase with increasing the temperature is present but with significant fluctuations. To understand this different behavior from that obtained in laboratory tests we must consider that the temperature interval in this field experiment is lower, and

the range of variation is shorter ($-1^{\circ}, 19^{\circ}$) with respect to that of the previous test ($14^{\circ}, 31^{\circ}$).

FIGURE 7. Temporal series of the interferometric phase retrieved from S1 IW SLC imagery. Different tones of grey of the graph background enhance the one-year lapse.

FIGURE 8. Interferometric phase in mm, vs air temperature and calculated fit line and corresponding correlation coefficient.

As far as the amplitude is concerned, considering the results of backscattering values discussed in the previous paragraph, the amplitude of the AR shows a certain instability, 0.84 dB. From the interferometric point of view, this seems not to significantly affect the phase stability which over the whole period of observation maintains within a two millimeters range of variation and a 0.5 mm of bias.

TABLE 3. Mean, STD max and min of the temporal series interferometric phase expressed in mm of LOS displacement and of the air temperature range.

Target	Mean	STD	Min	Max
AR Phase (mm)	0.50	2.11	-5	6
Air temperature (°C)	10	1.276	-1	19

In PS Interferometry, a parameter used to classify the PS quality is the dispersion of amplitude (DA): the lower is its value the higher its statistical reliability [1]; the low value (0.3) obtained for the AR confirms the high reliability of using this AR as a PS. Anyway, in order to investigate the causes of the detected amplitude fluctuations, which are also larger than obtained from the RF circuit performance in laboratory tests [17], we analyze the amplitude data values vs the temperature, as shown in fig. 9. The result shows a very low correlation to temperature, and this suggests investigating other potential causes for this uncertainty. One can be a random noise in the RF circuit not correlated to temperature; the second can be ascribed to an instable phase inherent to the scenario. We indeed decided to relate this instability to the observed scenario rather than to RF circuits behavior. Although when an outstanding target is present in the pixel area the amplitude and phase response of this target is dominant, a certain noise is however present. Considering the role of soil and in particular of the vegetation in radar backscattering at this frequency, distributed scatters in the vegetated areas could add significant fluctuations along the long temporal interval analyzed varying their geometrical and dielectric characteristics related to their phenological state (e.g. plant growth, soil moisture). To argue this hypothesis, we observe also the amplitude trend of the PCR used in the previous statistical characterization. This PCR shows a lower amplitude as expected, but fluctuations comparable to that of the AR: its mean and standard deviation are 1.6 db and 0.7 db respectively. This fact allows deducing that the thermal effect due to the internal circuit of the AR is of minor entity with respect to the scenario fluctuations, the only which can affect the PCR response. Furthermore, on the basis of the low correlation between phase data and atmospheric parameters resulting from fig.8, we can exclude that the temporal instability observed in the period can be ascribable to the effect of the atmospheric propagation, considering also that the applied interferometric processing includes an atmospheric correction based on the use of reference PSs close to the monitored area. Finally, we can estimate the value of the AR' RCS making a direct comparison between the RCS measured for the AR (table 2) and that for the PCR, 11.23db and 1.6db respectively (a difference greater than 9 dB). Assuming that RCS measured for the PCR corresponds to its theoretical maximum (32 dBsm), the RCS estimate for the AR is close to 41 dBsm, very close to the design requirement. With respect to the role of the SCR, the mean value obtained using the AR is sufficiently high to assure theoretically a high precision in phase measurements; using the SCR reported in

Table 1 and (1), we can evaluate a theoretical value lower than 0.5 mm. The final accuracy resulting from the statistical analysis is of a few millimeters (Table 2), dictated by the measured fluctuations of the phase over the long-concerned period. This significant difference can be also due to some influence of the observed amplitude temporal variation of the clutter resulting in the already mentioned 0.83dB amplitude instability. In conclusions, the role of the temperature variation on the active components of the RF section in this test appears less critical with respect to that observed in previous tests of the same device, but it is worth to note that the yearly temperature range of the climate of the site, and the use of descending geometry which corresponds to a pass of the satellite early in the morning (6 a.m. UCT), when the air temperature is almost at its daily minimum, avoided to acquire interferometric data in extremely high temperatures (higher than 20 °C). To investigate the influence of this factor additional observations based on the use of different orbit geometry (descending) or other climate conditions could be important.

FIGURE 9. AR Backscattering coefficient vs air temperature and calculated fit line; corresponding correlation coefficient is also indicated.

V. CONCLUSION

The goal of this study is to estimate the stability achievable from a low-cost AR using experimental data when used for deformation monitoring through InSAR. An analysis of the performance of the device designed to operate with C band spaceborne radars was carried out using Sentinel-1 imagery in a real field campaign. Temporal series obtained through an interferometric PS based processing were analyzed focusing on the stability of the amplitude and phase response of the AR and other significant targets, over a temporal interval almost three years long. The results allow achieving a fair understanding of the main causes of the AR instability. In particular, they allow quantifying on a statistical basis how the temperature of the device and other factors affect the stability

of the phase of the signal redirected by the AR to the satellite receiver. In previous studies the mayor drawback and the strongest limit to the employ of AR in field campaigns was identified in the sensitivity to temperature variations. In this specific case, due to the limited range of variation of temperature, the role of other factors as environmental aspects represented by the clutter fluctuations seems to have a mayor role. The analysis of the performance in amplitude and phase of the device allows estimating a stability in displacement measurement in about ± 2 mm, and a bias lower than 1 mm. This value can provide a performance acceptable for several applications of InSAR for landslides and deformation monitoring when the use of PCR is not feasible. However, to consolidate these results, further tests in situations where higher temperatures and wider range of variation should be experienced.

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